

CURRENT STATE OF EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS

Sayfiddinova Aziza

Fergana State University, English language department teacher

E-mail: say838670@mail.com

Kurbanova Gulnora Maqsadjonovna

Fergana State University

1st year student of the Faculty of Foreign Languages

E-mail: gulnora28092004@gmail.com

Annotation: Higher education is characterized by considerable breadth and variability in the field. Institutions differ in their history, size, population served, and various other factors. The following aspects are important for strategic planning initiatives in higher education. Obviously, many people or departments may be needed to carry out a particular action. However, if a group is identified as responsible, everyone in the group believes that someone else in the group will take responsibility. The implementation plan should be directive, clear and documented. The implementation of a strategic plan depends on the institution's ability to translate strategic ideas into rapid action. For this it is necessary.

Key words: Quick action, strategic ideas, initiatives, strategic planning, implementation plan.

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Communication is an important condition between organizations. Communication occurs in many different contexts, including interpersonal, group, organizational, and community contexts. It can be accidental or intentional, planned or unplanned. Communication is so natural and fundamental. In any number of higher education contexts, communication problems can be costly to the individual, group, and organization, leading to one or more of the following outcomes.

Higher education institutions bring together bright, highly educated and independent thinkers with interests and experience in a wide variety of fields and professional connections. The success of a university and its execution depend on many parties, so people are required not only to work independently and collaboratively, but also to create a strong campus. They must maintain close links with their technical or disciplinary fields of study, as well as interdisciplinary links to work effectively with faculty, staff, students, and external stakeholders.

Any strategy model for institutions should consider three levels, namely the strategic level, the operational level, and the tactical level in action. The strategic plan for any individual institution should focus on what is needed to help the institution realize its vision. If this vision is dominated by changes or improvements in academic performance, then this is the tool for

this plan. Institutional planners must understand that the purpose of a strategic plan is to focus on how resources will be allocated over a period of time in order to achieve a vision.

The strategic plan is focused on academic planning. The planning process must be successful in taking a strategic view of the organization and aligning relative resource needs with the institution's vision. The key to implementing the strategic plan at the functional levels of the institution is to transform the vision of the institution using operational and tactical planning. The advantage of an institution using its strategic plan to allocate resources is that everyone knows in advance which activities have priority and which will receive resources in any given year. The operational level is the planning carried out at the level of organizational units. In institutions where planning is not integrated, operational planning usually means that departments develop their own vision and their own list of critical resource needs. Tactical planning includes the guidelines, academic activities, and services needed for effective management, planning, budgeting, and evaluation. Operational guidelines and the academic activities and services of offices and departments across campus are an unwritten legacy of institutional traditions and may be inconsistently applied or changed by anyone at any time for any reason.

Both the requirements and the shortcomings of higher education affect the future employment of students who have already received the corresponding degree in higher education. It is necessary to analyze and change the evaluation system, which must comply with the international standard. In addition, higher education policy should be designed with a focus on current issues and facts.

A well-designed and implemented strategic planning process can provide an institution with a forum for university-wide discussion of important decisions. This process can also be organized in a way that facilitates assessment, resource allocation and accreditation, as well as being a source of progress and achievement information of great value to those associated with the institution.

Higher education can reinvent itself to prepare students for social challenges in both traditional, well-established ways and in ways based on new technologies, bringing together expertise from multiple disciplines through the development of a strategic plan within the institution. Thus, the institution will need to demonstrate greater responsibility and greater commitment to all stakeholders once it becomes autonomous.

Strategic planning is essential to the success of higher education institutions because it allows the institution to analyze the current state and predict the future. This is essential for the formation of institutional culture in the intuition of higher education. A good strategic planning process in higher education requires sufficient time from leaders, faculty and other stakeholders. Clearly, institutions need to determine their capabilities and be prepared to allocate an appropriate amount of time in the strategic planning process.

The success of a strategic plan can be judged not only by the quality of the document and the specifics of the formal plan, but also by the inclusiveness of the process. Feelings of ownership and ownership of the goals, plans, implementation and outcomes resulting from efforts also need to be analyzed.

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